

Theoretical Model for a Randomized
Controlled Trial on AMBAR Therapy in
Preclinical Alzheimer's Disease:
Neuropsychological and Biomarker-Based
Evaluation

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ABSTRACT

Background: Alzheimer's disease (AD) is marked by the accumulation of amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) plaques and TAU protein neurofibrillary tangles, up to a decade before the onset of clinical symptoms. For those in the final preclinical stage of AD, known as phase 3 preclinical AD (P3-PAD), studies have shown a 56% progression to dementia within five years, underscoring the critical need for early intervention strategies. AMBAR (Alzheimer's Management by Albumin Replacement) therapy, is founded on the "peripheral sink hypothesis," suggesting that modulating peripheral $A\beta$ levels attenuates cerebral amyloid. Data from the Ambar trial, show that later-stage AD patients treated with AMBAR show approximately a 60% deceleration in cognitive decline compared to placebo, prompting investigation into its potential during the disease's early stages. Therefore, this study's aim is to assess AMBAR's efficacy in delaying cognitive decline over 26 months in P3-PAD patients.

Methods: We will conduct a multicenter, blinded, placebo-controlled trial across 18 centers in Spain, enrolling around 237 individuals aged 50-85, exhibiting cognitive decline predictive of P3-PAD, and positive biomarkers (A+T+N+ or A+T+N-) indicative of likely progression to clinical Alzheimer's within the 26-month study timeframe. Participants will be sourced from primary care facilities (CAP), neurological services, or through self-referral. Cognitive performance changes, our primary endpoint, will be assessed using the Preclinical Alzheimer Cognitive Composite (PACC) and Free and Cued Selective Reminding test (FCSRT), alongside Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) assessments. Longitudinal mean scores will be analyzed via repeated-measures ANOVA, examining the treatment's efficacy. Secondary outcomes will track alterations in AD-specific and general neuroinflammatory and neurodegenerative biomarkers.

Expected Results: AMBAR therapy is posited to reduce the rate of cognitive decline in P3-PAD patients significantly, aiming for a medium to large effect size (cohen's d [0.5, 0.8]) at a 0.05 significance level. We expect treated patients to exhibit improved biomarker profiles, alongside stabilized or enhanced life quality. The study will further explore a "dose-response" relationship, hypothesizing that increased therapy dosage will correlate with better cognitive outcomes.

Success in this trial could mark a turning point in early-stage Alzheimer's intervention, potentially reshaping the prognosis for preclinical AD. This could lead to prolonged maintenance of social functions and quality of life, lower healthcare costs, destigmatization of dementia, and inspire a more dignified perspective on aging.

Keywords: "Alzheimer's disease", "Cognition Disorders", "cognitive decline", "Randomized Controlled Trials", "Neuropsychological Tests", "Biological Markers" [MeSH], "Early Intervention", "Phase 3 Preclinical AD", "Preclinical Alzheimer's Cognitive Composite" (PACC), "Free and Cued Selective Reminding test" (FCSRT).

RESUM

Antecedents: La malaltia d'Alzheimer (EA) es caracteritza per l'acumulació de plaques d'amieloide-beta ($A\beta$) i embulls neurofibril·lars de proteïna TAU fins a una dècada abans de l'inici dels símptomes clínics. Per a aquells en la fase final preclínica de l'EA, coneguda com a fase 3 preclínica de l'EA (P3-PAD), els estudis han mostrat un progrés del 56% cap a la demència en 5 anys, subratllant la necessitat crítica d'estratègies d'intervenció primerenca. La teràpia AMBAR (Maneig de l'Alzheimer mitjançant Reemplaçament d'Albúmina), basada en la "peripheral sink hypothesis", suggereix que modular els nivells perifèrics d' $A\beta$ atenua l'amieloide cerebral. Les dades de l'assaig Ambar indiquen que pacients amb EA en etapes tardanes tractats amb AMBAR mostren una desacceleració aproximada del 60% en el declivi cognitiu comparat amb placebo, motivant la investigació del seu potencial durant les etapes primerenques de la malaltia. Per tant, l'objectiu d'aquest estudi és avaluar l'eficàcia d'AMBAR en retardar el declivi cognitiu durant 26 mesos en pacients amb P3-PAD.

Mètodes: Realitzarem un assaig multicèntric, cec, controlat amb placebo a 18 centres a Espanya, inscrivint al voltant de 237 individus d'edats entre 50-85 anys, mostrant declivi cognitiu predictiu de P3-PAD, i biomarcadors positius (A+T+N+ o A+T+N-) indicatius d'una probable progressió cap a l'EA clínica dins del període d'estudi de 26 mesos. Els participants seran captats de centres d'atenció primària (CAP), serveis neurològics o mitjançant auto-referència. Els canvis en el rendiment cognitiu, el nostre objectiu primari, seran avaluats utilitzant el Compost Cognitiu Preclínic de l'Alzheimer (PACC) i la prova de Recordatori Selectiu Lliure i Amb Pista (FCSRT), juntament amb les avaluacions de l'Examen de l'Estat Mental Mínim (MMSE). Les puntuacions mitjanes longitudinals seran analitzades mitjançant ANOVA de mesures repetides, examinant l'eficàcia del tractament. Els resultats secundaris seguiran les alteracions en biomarcadors específics de l'EA i biomarcadors neuroinflamatoris i neurodegeneratius generals.

Resultats Esperats: Es postula que la teràpia AMBAR reduirà significativament la taxa de declivi cognitiu en pacients amb P3-PAD, apuntant a una mida d'efecte

mitjana a gran (d de cohen [0.5, 0.8]) amb un nivell de significància de 0.05. Esperem que els pacients tractats exhibeixin perfils de biomarcadors millorats, juntament amb una qualitat de vida estabilitzada o millorada. L'estudi explorarà a més una relació "dosi-resposta", hipotetitzant que una major dosi de teràpia es correlacionarà amb millors resultats cognitius. L'èxit en aquest assaig podria marcar un punt d'inflexió en la intervenció de l'EA en etapes primerenques, potencialment canviant el pronòstic per a l'EA preclínica. Això podria conduir al manteniment prolongat de les funcions socials i la qualitat de vida, reduir els costos d'atenció mèdica, desestigmatitzar la demència i inspirar una perspectiva més digna sobre l'envelliment.

Paraules clau: "malaltia d'Alzheimer", "Trastorns Cognitius", "declivi cognitiu", "Assajos Controlats Aleatoritzats", "Proves Neuropsicològiques", "Marcadors Biològics", "Intervenció Precoç", "Fase 3 Preclínica EA", "Compost Cognitiu Preclínic d'Alzheimer" (PACC), "Prova de Recordatori Selectiu Lliure i Dirigit" (FCSRT)

RESUMEN

Antecedentes: La enfermedad de Alzheimer (EA) se caracteriza por la acumulación de placas de amiloide-beta ($A\beta$) y ovillos neurofibrilares de proteína TAU hasta una década antes del inicio de los síntomas clínicos. Para aquellos en la fase final preclínica de la EA, conocida como fase 3 preclínica de la EA (P3-PAD), los estudios han mostrado un progreso del 56% hacia la demencia en 5 años, resaltando la necesidad crítica de estrategias de intervención temprana. La terapia AMBAR (Manejo de la Alzheimer mediante Reemplazo de Albúmina), basada en la "peripheral sink hypothesis", sugiere que modular los niveles periféricos de $A\beta$ atenúa el amiloide cerebral. Datos del ensayo Ambar indican que pacientes con EA en etapas tardías tratados con AMBAR muestran una deceleración aproximada del 60% en el declive cognitivo comparado con el placebo, motivando la investigación de su potencial durante las etapas tempranas de la enfermedad. Por lo tanto, el objetivo de este estudio es evaluar la eficacia de AMBAR en retrasar el declive cognitivo durante 26 meses en pacientes con P3-PAD.

Métodos: Realizaremos un ensayo multicéntrico, ciego, controlado con placebo en 18 centros en España, inscribiendo alrededor de 237 individuos de 50-85 años, mostrando declive cognitivo predictivo de P3-PAD, y biomarcadores positivos (A+T+N+ o A+T+N-) indicativos de una probable progresión a la EA clínica dentro del periodo de estudio de 26 meses. Los participantes serán reclutados de centros de atención primaria (CAP), servicios neurológicos o mediante auto-referencia. Los cambios en el rendimiento cognitivo, nuestro objetivo primario, se evaluarán utilizando el Compuesto Cognitivo Preclínico de Alzheimer (PACC) y la prueba de Recordatorio Selectivo Libre y Guiado (FCSRT), junto con las evaluaciones del Examen del Estado Mental Mínimo (MMSE). Las puntuaciones medias se analizarán mediante ANOVA de medidas repetidas, examinando la eficacia del tratamiento. Los resultados secundarios seguirán las alteraciones en biomarcadores específicos de la EA y biomarcadores neuroinflamatorios y neurodegenerativos generales.

Resultados Esperados: Se postula que la terapia AMBAR reducirá significativamente la tasa de declive cognitivo en pacientes con P3-PAD, apuntando

a un tamaño de efecto medio a grande (d de cohen [0.5, 0.8]) con un nivel de significancia de 0.05. Esperamos que los pacientes tratados exhiban perfiles de biomarcadores mejorados, junto con una calidad de vida estabilizada o mejorada. El estudio explorará además una relación "dosis-respuesta", hipotetizando que una mayor dosis de terapia se correlacionará con mejores resultados cognitivos. El éxito en este ensayo podría marcar un punto de inflexión en la intervención de la EA en etapas tempranas, potencialmente cambiando el pronóstico para la EA preclínica. Esto podría llevar al mantenimiento prolongado de las funciones sociales y la calidad de vida, reducir los costos de atención médica, desestigmatizar la demencia e inspirar una perspectiva más digna sobre el envejecimiento.

Palabras clave: "enfermedad de Alzheimer", "Trastornos Cognitivos", "declive cognitivo", "Ensayos Controlados Aleatorizados", "Pruebas Neuropsicológicas", "Marcadores Biológicos", "Intervención Temprana", "Fase 3 Preclínica EA", "Compuesto Cognitivo Preclínico de Alzheimer" (PACC), "Prueba de Recordatorio Selectivo Libre y Guiado" (FCSRT).

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INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is an irreversible, progressive neurological condition that hinders an individual's daily activities and social interactions. With the rise in life expectancy and an aging population, Alzheimer's disease is anticipated to continue increasing worldwide, particularly in developing nations, resulting in a substantial healthcare and economic burden (1). Notably, in Spain, the number of people affected by dementia currently exceeds 700,000, with projections for 2050 expecting a doubling of cases to nearly two million individuals (2). It is important to recognize that AD is characterized by a gradual and protracted development spanning several years to decades (3). Its progression is marked by the progressive accumulation of amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) plaques and TAU protein neurofibrillary tangles, associated with neuro-inflammation and neuronal loss, ultimately leading to cognitive impairment (4). Thereupon, the implementation of an early approach and management plays a pivotal role in optimizing its treatment and care, as it allows for interventions and support that can potentially slow its progression and improve the quality of life for affected individuals. Understanding that as many as 56% of individuals in the late preclinical stages of Alzheimer's disease may progress to full-blown dementia within five years provides a compelling reason for examining the efficacy of AMBAR “Alzheimer’s Management by Albumin Replacement” therapy in this early stage (5). However, recognizing the initial signs of Alzheimer's can be challenging, especially when cognitive test results appear normal.

According to the US National Institute on Aging-Alzheimer’s Association (NIA-AA) framework, AD begins with a preclinical stage, marking the silent onset of the disease. During this phase, individuals may notice changes in cognition, yet standard assessments tests often show no impairment. The subsequent stage, Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI), manifests with mild but measurable cognitive decline on standard tests, alongside positive biomarkers. Ultimately, the transition to dementia brings pronounced cognitive deficits that are both clinically evident and biomarker confirmed (6).

Within the preclinical phase, a further subdivision is recognized, comprising three stages: the first two stages involve the presence of AD-related biomarkers without

noticeable cognitive decline. While the third stage, known as phase 3 preclinical AD (P3-PAD), is marked by the emergence of cognitive impairment that fall short of the criteria for an MCI diagnosis. During this stage, compensatory mechanisms play a paramount role in preserving performance levels on specific individual tests while concealing the cognitive decline (6,7).

Embracing the NIA-AA's framework, this randomized controlled trial (RCT) will adopt the ATN classification system to select participants. This system evaluates AD's biomarkers in three distinct groups: Amyloid pathology (A), Tau pathology (T), and Neurodegeneration or neuronal injury (N). Our inclusion criteria will include individuals classified as A+T+N+ and A+T+N-, pinpointing those most likely to exhibit disease progression within the study's 26-month duration. This precise differentiation is strategic for yielding valuable insights into patient progression and comparing the effectiveness of treatment against control groups.

The manifestations of P3-PAD often go unnoticed by conventional cognitive assessments like the Alzheimer's Disease Assessment Scale-Cognitive Subscale (ADAS-Cog) due to their lack of sensitivity to early cognitive changes (8). To bridge this gap, a range of "composite measures" are at the forefront of cognitive assessment for P3-PAD, combining multiple cognitive domains, such as memory, executive function, and attention into a single indicator with enhanced sensitivity and validity for early detection. These cognitive batteries such as the Preclinical Alzheimer's Cognitive Composite (PACC) or the Free and Cued Selective Reminding test (FCSRT), have shown an Area Under the Curve of 0.771 and 0.764 respectively, with sensitivities and specificities around 70%, reflecting their accuracy and robust statistical profile for identifying P3-PAD. These composites reflect a strong internal consistency and applicability, making them particularly effective in tracking progression with precise ROC curves, intrinsic to cater to the subtle cognitive changes, enabling targeted interventions and improved patient prognoses (9).

As research is converging on the consensus that intervention strategies should precede the MCI stage to counteract the disease's progression effectively, this early detection is vital. A perspective fueled by mounting evidence that A β accumulation

begins well over a decade before MCI manifests, during or even preceding the preclinical phase when interventions could be more impactful (10). Therefore, the most promising window for therapeutic intervention precedes the MCI phase; In vivo studies have highlighted a sobering reality: once neurodegeneration has set in firmly, anti-A β therapies may have limited efficacy (11). This mirrors the concept of early intervention in other chronic conditions, such as diabetes, where preemptive measures can significantly alter the disease's trajectory.

Consequently, in light of the evolving paradigm shift towards a biological definition of AD, and despite ongoing debates, the amyloid hypothesis remains a cornerstone in Alzheimer's research, with recent biomarker advancements reinforcing its relevance in early detection and intervention strategies.

The integration of topographical and pathophysiological biomarkers is essential for the early detection and monitoring of preclinical AD. For instance, serial magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and Fluorodeoxyglucose Positron Emission Tomography (FDG-PET) imaging offer key insights into the brain structure, metabolism, and small vessel disease, while white matter hyperintensities (WMH) reveals patterns of neural activity and vascular health for a better understanding of the progression of the disease (12).

Moreover, plasma and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) biomarkers are intrinsic to a narrow follow-up of AD, especially during its preclinical stage and as it progresses. By measuring levels of specific proteins in the CSF, such as A β 42, A β 40, phosphorylated Tau (p-Tau) 181, p-Tau217, and total Tau (T-Tau), we can closely monitor the onset and progression of neuroinflammation and neurodegeneration (13). Simultaneously, plasma biomarkers offer a minimally invasive way to track neurodegeneration. Neurofilament light chain (NFL) and p-Tau 217 are particularly indicative of AD, providing a focused view of the disease's development. Additionally, plasma levels of Glial Fibrillary Acidic Protein (GFAP) are evaluated for signs of neuroinflammation, contributing to a broader understanding of AD's pathology (14,15,16).

Recent advancements in AD research have marked a pivotal transition in our understanding and treatment of this complex condition. With the U.S. FDA's approval

of monoclonal antibodies like lecanemab and aducanumab, we are witnessing a upsurge of side effects intricately linked with their potential induction of inflammation, which in many cases can manifest as amyloid-related imaging abnormalities (ARIA), with edema (ARIA-E) and microbleeds (ARIA-H) being notable concerns (17). This association is deeply rooted in the mechanism of action of these antibodies and their interaction with the cerebral vasculature, thus posing a significant challenge in their clinical application.

Conversely, the therapeutic philosophy underpinning albumin plasmapheresis diverges fundamentally from this approach. Given its inherent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties (18), albumin plasmapheresis is posited as a treatment that could circumvent the pro-inflammatory pathways activated by monoclonal antibodies, potentially mitigating the risk of ARIA. This treatment modality hinges on the “peripheral sink hypothesis” and suggests that by rebalancing amyloid-beta levels in the peripheral circulation, one could achieve a therapeutic reduction in cerebral amyloid without invoking the inflammatory responses typically seen with antibody therapies (19,20,21).

The therapeutic underpinning of AMBAR “Alzheimer’s Management by Albumin Replacement” rests on this principle. It theorizes that plasma exchange with Albutein®, a high-purity albumin devoid of A β , may facilitate the efflux of soluble A β from the brain to the blood, utilizing albumin’s capacity to bind up to approximately 90% of plasma A β (22). It is, however, important to underscore that the definitive impact of albumin plasmapheresis on ARIA incidence remains to be conclusively determined. Likewise, AMBAR therapy, characterized as generally safe within clinical AD, it carries known risks, with the most frequent adverse events being local catheter reactions, hypotension, muscle spasms, and anemia, among others, all of which are manageable through vigilant monitoring and timely intervention (23,24). While such data is not yet available for preclinical AD, it is reasonable to speculate a similar safety profile, given the continuous nature of AD's pathology.

Thus, its well-established safety profile, underlined by its preventive and manageable nature, ensures ethical appropriateness and practical viability for treating individuals in the earliest stages of Alzheimer's disease, where symptoms are minimal and intervention is most beneficial.

Given that AMBAR trials have indicated a substantial 60% deceleration in cognitive decline for patients with mild to moderate stages of Alzheimer's, this RCT strategically targets the preclinical stages, where therapeutic intervention is posited to offer maximal benefit (24). Hence, this randomized controlled trial of albumin plasmapheresis stands as a crucial and innovative element of “secondary prevention” in AD, intervening before the transition from P3-PAD to MCI. By rigorously evaluating the impact of albumin plasmapheresis at this early juncture, the aim is to establish a foundational approach for altering the course of the disease at a stage where it may be most amenable to treatment.

OBJECTIVES

Main objective

To evaluate the efficacy and dose-response relationship of AMBAR in delaying cognitive decline over a 26-month period in patients with phase 3 preclinical AD, comparing outcomes across two treatment groups and a control group, measured through comprehensive neuropsychological assessments and biomarker analyses.

Secondary objectives

- To evaluate how education impacts individual thresholds of AD biomarkers and influence the clinical response to AMBAR treatment.
- To evaluate how genetic risk factors (APOE ϵ 4 status) impacts individual thresholds of AD biomarkers and influence the clinical response to AMBAR treatment.
- To evaluate patients' tolerability and adherence during treatment.
- To evaluate patients' quality of life during treatment.

HYPOTHESIS

Main hypothesis

AMBAR therapy will delay cognitive decline in patients with phase 3 preclinical AD over a 26-month period. Furthermore, we anticipate a dose-response relationship, with higher doses of AMBAR showing greater efficacy in delaying cognitive decline, as measured through comprehensive neuropsychological assessments and biomarker analyses.

Secondary hypothesis

- Individual responses to AMBAR therapy, and AD biomarker thresholds will vary according to educational status.
- Individual responses to AMBAR therapy, and AD biomarker thresholds will vary according to the modulating effects of APOE ϵ 4 status.
- Patients undergoing AMBAR treatment will show high tolerability and adherence throughout the treatment course.
- Patients undergoing AMBAR treatment will show sustained or enhanced quality of life throughout the treatment course, as measured by the Quality of Life in Alzheimer's Disease (QoL-AD) questionnaire.

METHODS

Trial design

This study will be a multicenter, blinded, placebo-controlled, parallel-group study aimed at assessing the superiority of Plasma Exchange with Albumin Replacement and Intravenous Immunoglobulin compared to placebo. It will be conducted in 18 sites throughout Spain (**annex 3**).

Patients are individually randomized in a 1:1:1 allocation ratio to receive either one of the two different doses of albumin and intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG) or placebo, ensuring a balanced comparison across the three groups. Patients' progression will be assessed through neuropsychological assessments and biomarker measures over a 26-month period.

This study will employ a stratified design based on participants' APOE4 status (carrier or non-carrier) and educational level (superior education yes or no).

This protocol was developed in accordance with the guidelines provided by the CONSORT 2010 Explanation and Elaboration document (25).

Important changes to methods after trial commencement.

In the course of this trial, should we encounter specific challenges during the trial, protocol modifications may be considered, supported by thorough justifications. For instance, to address slower-than-anticipated recruitment rates, we may extend the recruitment period by an additional six months beyond the initially planned 12-month timeframe. Expanding to additional clinical sites could also be contemplated to meet enrollment targets.

In the event of significant adverse effects, particularly within the high-dose albumin group, we will implement intensified safety monitoring protocols and consult with the independent Data Monitoring Committee regarding possible dosage adjustments or the discontinuation of the high-dose group, potentially leading to a revised allocation ratio of 2:1 (Low albumin:control).

These potential changes will be implemented only after thorough deliberation and consultation, without compromising the blinding of outcome assessments, and ensuring that any modifications are based on solid evidence and are in the best interest of participant safety and study integrity.

Eligibility criteria for participants

Participants are primarily referred by general practitioners in a primary care settings, neurology specialists, or may self-refer to the study center. Participants will have the chance to go over the participant information document and sign the consent form, thereby agreeing to partake in the study and permitting their data to be utilized.

Inclusion criteria

Participants eligible for this study are adults aged 50-85 at the time of signing the informed consent. Inclusion criteria comprise patients with positive AD biomarkers demonstrated by CSF and plasma tests, we will include individuals classified as A+T+N+ and A+T+N-. Cognitive function should demonstrate a cognitive decline (memory/language/executive function) reported by the patient and measured by the Preclinical Alzheimer Cognitive Composite (PACC) or the Free and Cued Selective

Reminding Test (FCSRT), with scores >1.5 standard deviations below the norm for age, gender, and education level. A recent (within 12 months) brain computerized tomography (CT) or MRI must verify the absence of cerebrovascular disease and rule out exclusionary conditions such as microhemorrhages, infarctions, hematomas, strokes, or brain tumors.

Exclusion criteria

Exclusion criteria are patients with mild or moderate cognitive impairment or dementia (MMSE < 26). Patients with any contraindications for plasmapheresis, including behavioral disorders, difficult venous access, abnormal coagulation; adverse reactions to blood components, or hypersensitivity to albumin or components of Albutein® or Flebogamma® DIF; IgA deficiency; refractory anemia with hemoglobin levels <10 g/dL; renal impairment with plasma creatinine >2 mg/dL; uncontrolled hypertension (>160/100mmHg) despite treatment over the last 3 months; significant liver disease (GPT >2.5 times the upper limit of normal (ULN), or bilirubin >2 mg/dL); any heart disease; any illness with less than one year projected survival; current substance abuse; and status as pregnant or nursing (23).

Settings and locations where the data were collected.

The study will be conducted at 18 sites in Spain (**annex 3**) with the coordinating center established at the Research Center and Memory Clinic Fundació ACE - Institut Català de Neurociències Aplicades in Barcelona. ACE was selected for its expertise in Alzheimer's disease, other neurodegenerative diseases and clinical research. This study's multicentric approach is designed to capture a broad sample of individuals at the earliest stages of AD, which, while prevalent, often go unrecognized.

The interventions for each group

In this study, we have adapted the "AMBAR treatment protocol" (23) to better suit the gradual development of preclinical phase 3 AD.

This RCT incorporates three distinct treatment arms, and patients will partake in an initial 6-week period of intensive therapeutic plasma exchange (TPE) with weekly

sessions. This will be followed by a year-long phase of low volume plasma exchange (LVPE) with monthly interventions. Uniquely, this study extends to 26 months, which includes an additional 12-month observational follow-up to evaluate disease progression.

The tailored TPE involves exchanging 2500 to 3000 mL of the patient's plasma for an equivalent volume of Albutein® 5%, while the LVPE process substitutes 650 to 880 mL of plasma with Albutein® 20%. Dosages of albumin for LVPE are determined by the assigned treatment arm (20gr vs 40gr), with alternate administrations of Flebogamma® DIF 5% varying between 10 and 20 grams.

TPE is performed with a commercial cell separator, customized to patient characteristics for selecting the venous access site. The exchange volume is also personalized, ranging between 25-35 ml/kg, thus approximating 1500-2000 ml per session. Facility-specific protocols govern the venous access management, with placement validation through radiographic confirmation.

For the LVPE, peripheral lines and advanced apheresis technology modeled after the Auto-C™ and Aurora™ systems are employed. The plasma volume removed aligns with typical plasma donation quantities and is adjusted according to the patient's body mass. Any discrepancies in volume between the plasma removed and albumin returned are compensated with saline, adhering to the specific treatment group's protocols (23).

The procedural timeframe is designed with flexibility to cater to the individual schedules of patients, allowing for a ± 2 day window in the intensive phase and ± 3 days in follow-up assessments, reinforcing the commitment to patient-centric care while strictly observing the study protocol.

Regarding the sham treatment, the procedure superficially replicates TPE without actual plasma being involved. A nonfunctional catheter lookalike is affixed to the participant using an adhesive patch, placed at typical catheter sites. In this arm, a saline solution tinted to look like plasma circulates within the apparatus, providing a visual and procedural facsimile of the TPE method. In a parallel fashion, the sham

version of LVPE uses a mock apheresis device, designed to echo the operational characteristics of specific industry-standard systems, circulating non-viable blood within a sealed circuit. This maintains the illusion of the LVPE process . Rigorous training sessions and detailed visual guides are provided to personnel to ensure that sham and actual procedures are performed with a level of uniformity that preserves the blinding of both participants and those evaluating outcomes (23).

This intervention protocol, along with its methodological decisions, stems from conclusions drawn from the pilot and phase II/III studies of the AMBAR protocol (23,24).

Defined pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures.

Primary Outcome Assessment

In this RCT, our primary outcome is the change in cognitive performance over 26 months as measured by the PACC and the FCSRT.

Participants will be divided into three groups: Group 1 (G1), Group 2 (G2), and a Control group.

This study aims to evaluate the efficacy of AMBAR in delaying the cognitive decline as measured by these composite measures. The analysis will primarily focus on changes in PACC and FCSRT scores to ascertain differences in cognitive performance trajectories among the study groups over the 26-month period. While the MMSE will also be administered as part of the comprehensive cognitive assessment battery, its role will be supplementary given its relatively lower sensitivity to early cognitive changes (26,27).

Secondary Outcome Assessment

Cerebral metabolism and structural changes in hippocampal volume, posterior cingulate volume, WMH and other areas of interest as shown by MRI will be monitored via neuroimaging at baseline, at week 6 and at the end of the maintenance and follow up phases respectively.

Concurrently, PET-FDG scans and CSF protein levels of A β ₄₂/A β ₄₀ ratio, T-tau, P-Tau 181, and P-tau 217 will be conducted at the same checkpoints, to gauge biomarker variations.

Blood will be drawn before and after each PE to monitor adverse effects, plasma levels of GFAP, NFL, p-Tau 217 and A β ₄₂/A β ₄₀ ratio.

The different assessment checkpoints are described in **annex 4** for a more comprehensive understanding.

Other Assessments

Secondary outcomes include the incidence of treatment-related adverse events, which will be collected throughout the study duration. Adherence rates will be monitored through patient self-reports and treatment logs. APOE ϵ 4 status and education level's influence on treatment efficacy will be analyzed through subgroup analyses.

Patient adherence and tolerability will be monitored as vital aspects of the trial's overall assessment.

Quality of life will be measured using the Quality of Life in Alzheimer's Disease (QoL-AD) questionnaire at baseline, and every 6 months during the maintenance phase and the follow-up period. This tool is designed to assess the quality of life in individuals with dementia. It comprises 13 items that participants rate as 'poor,' 'fair,' 'good,' or 'excellent,' with scoring ranging from 1 to 4 for each item, summing to a total maximum score of 52 (28). Further details regarding the questionnaire can be found below

Neuropsychological composite measures and questionnaires

The PACC and FCSRT assessments are chosen for their high sensitivity to the early, subtle declines in cognitive functions characteristic of the transition from preclinical to clinical AD. They are designed to provide a comprehensive evaluation of cognitive domains most likely to be affected in the early stages of AD, offering a complete understanding of disease progression :

-PACC :The table below presents the components of the PACC, a composite measure sensitive to the subtle cognitive changes indicative of preclinical Alzheimer's disease. The listed components reflect its specific cognitive domains and their respective weights within the composite score (29). For a deeper exploration of each test, please refer to the **annex 5** which provides expanded explanations.

Component	Domain	Weight
Symbol Digit Modalities	Perceptual Speed/Working Memory	0.26
MMSE Orientation to Time	Orientation	2.24
MMSE Orientation to Place	Orientation	2.14
Logical Memory Delayed Recall	Episodic Memory	0.53
Word List-Delayed Recall	Episodic Memory	1.36
Judgment of Line Orientation	Visual Spatial	0.68
Raven's Progressive Matrices (9 items from A and B)	Visual Spatial	1.39

Acknowledging the importance of preserving test validity through the translation process, adapting the PACC into Spanish is guided by rigorous standards for neuropsychological test adaptation, ensuring that its validity remains intact for Spanish-speaking populations. This approach aligns with recognized methodologies and ensures that the PACC remains a reliable tool for assessing cognitive function among Spanish-speaking populations (30).

-The FCSRT involves a series of three recall trials:

Study Phase: The subject is first presented with cards containing pictures, categorized under unique cues (e.g., grapes under the fruit category), and asked to remember these items.

Immediate Cued Recall: After identification, there's an immediate recall check for these items, providing retrieval practice while the information is still fresh in working memory.

Recall Trials: Following the study phase, the subject goes through three recall trials. Each trial consists of:

- **Free Recall:** The subject is asked to recall the items from memory without any cues.

- **Cued Recall:** If items cannot be freely recalled, cues are then provided to help with the recall.

The process, including both free recall and cued recall, is repeated across three separate trials, and each trial is followed by a short interference task. The cumulative sum of items recalled freely across the three trials gives the "free recall" score, and the cumulative sum of both free recall and cued recall across the three trials constitutes the "total recall" score. Both of these scores have a potential range from 0 to 48. "Cue efficiency" is a ratio that measures the success of cued recall relative to the total possible cued recalls, providing an efficiency score ranging from 0.0 to 1.0. (31)

The FCSRT version used has been validated for Spanish-speaking populations, ensuring cultural and linguistic appropriateness and accuracy in measuring cognitive function among Spanish-speaking participants (32).

-The **MMSE** includes eleven questions and requires only 5-10 minutes to administer, making it practical for serial and routine use. It concentrates solely on the cognitive aspects of mental functions, excluding questions related to mood, abnormal mental experiences, and the form of thinking. Within its cognitive scope, it is thorough, providing a simplified, scored form of the cognitive mental status examination known as the "Mini-Mental State" (MMSE). As signaled previously, despite its widespread use, the MMSE is subject to certain limitations as it may not adequately assess cognitive impairment in early stages without supplementary evaluation tools (28). For more details consult **annex 6**.

The MMSE has been validated for Spanish-speaking populations, ensuring its appropriateness and reliability for cognitive function evaluation in this demographic group (33).

- **The QoL-AD:** The Quality of Life in Alzheimer's Disease questionnaire is an interview-administered tool designed to assess the quality of life in individuals with dementia. The QoL-AD is a tool designed to capture the perceived quality of life in individuals with AD. It is usually administered through a structured interview either

with the subject or an informant, ideally in a private setting. The respondent is provided with the questionnaire to refer to while the interviewer reads out each item. Respondents are asked to evaluate various life aspects, such as physical health, mood, memory, and family relationships, rating them as 'poor,' 'fair,' 'good,' or 'excellent.'

Throughout the process, it's essential that the respondent has a clear understanding of each item. If uncertainty or inability to rate a specific aspect arises, they are encouraged to make an estimate or best guess. Interviewers should not suggest answers but should ensure that the respondent comprehends the questions to give accurate ratings.

The respondent's autonomy is respected by allowing them to hold their copy of the questionnaire, ensuring they can follow along and participate actively.

For more detailed information and to view the questionnaire itself, please refer to **annex 7**.

Study's Schedule

Phases of the Treatment	Recruitment & Eligibility screening	BV	Phases of the Treatment																					
			Weeks of the study						Months of the study															
Timeline	Month -12 to 0		1	2	3	4	5	6	FV	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	FV	18	22	26	
Intensive Phase (PE)																								
Maintenance Phase																								
Follow-up Phase																								
Blood analysis																								
Lumbar puncture																								
MRI																								
PET-FDG																								
PACC + FCSRT + MMSE + QoL-AD																								
Plasma exchange with 5% Albutein																								
Plasma exchange with 20% Albutein (20 grams vs 40 grams)																								
Intravenous Inmunoglobulin (10 grams vs 20 grams)																								

How sample size was determined

Accepting an alpha risk of 0.05 and a power of 0.8 in a one-tailed test 79 subjects are necessary in each group to recognize as statistically significant a minimum difference of 0.5 units between any pair of groups assuming that 3 exist. The common deviation is assumed to be 1. A drop-out rate of 10% has been anticipated. To recruit this number of patients a 12-month inclusion period is set.

Interim analyses and stopping guidelines.

Interim analyses will be conducted at specific points (**annex 4**) in the study to assess the effectiveness and safety of the intervention. We will use the O'Brien-Fleming method to control for Type I error rates, ensuring that we only stop the trial early for very strong evidence of benefit or harm. This method is well-established and respected in clinical research, providing a precise statistical framework for our decision-making process (34).

Intervention halt may occur due to significant protocol deviations, adverse events, withdrawal, or loss to follow-up, ensuring adherence to ethical standards and study integrity.

Study termination will be considered if interim results indicate efficacy or harm, participant retention compromises study power, or external evidence resolves the research question.

Specifically, if severe adverse events affect more than 10% of participants in any group, or if treatment groups experience a significantly higher rate of severe events than the control group, or in the event of any treatment-related deaths, an immediate halt and review will be implemented. The committee will compare these events against the anticipated risk profile to decide on the trial's continuation.

Method used to generate the random allocation sequence.

The sequence generation for randomization will be conducted using a computerized random number generator. The randomization sequence will be conducted by block randomization method with blocks of six to ensure equal group sizes. The process is

stratified by two factors: APOE ϵ 4 status (carrier or non-carrier) and level of educational attainment (superior education or not). For each stratum defined by these factors, a separate block randomization scheme will be utilized.

Type of randomization; details of any restriction

Block randomization with fixed block sizes of six (2A, 2B and 2C) will be used to maintain balanced group sizes throughout the trial. This method is applied separately within each category of the stratification factors, requiring a distinct set of randomization sequences for each stratum ensuring comparability between groups.

Mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence

Allocation will be concealed using sequentially numbered, sealed envelopes prepared by an independent administrator. Participants will be enrolled by assessing their eligibility and obtaining informed consent. After enrollment, an independent administrator will assign interventions using a predetermined randomization process (block of 6 with all possible permutations). This involves the opening of the next sequential, sealed envelope which contains the group allocation. The designated intervention, whether it is the active treatment or the sham, will then be administered according to the protocol.

From Enrollment to Intervention Assignment

The allocation sequence was generated by an independent statistician using a computerized random number generator, ensuring no clinical involvement in the trial. This sequence incorporates stratification by APOE ϵ 4 status and education level and utilizing block randomization to maintain balance. Participants are enrolled by research staff who assess eligibility and obtain informed consent, without access to the randomization sequence. Following enrollment, an independent coordinator, not involved in the assessment or care of the participants, assigns them to their groups based on the sequence contained within sequentially numbered, sealed envelopes. This process ensures complete separation between sequence generation, allocation concealment, and implementation of assignments.

Blinding

In this study, participants, outcome assessors, doctors and data analysts will be blinded to the allocation of interventions. Participants will receive either the active treatment or a sham intervention, both administered in a way that appears identical to ensure blinding. Care providers will administer the treatment without disclosing details to participants or assessors. Data analysts will work with coded data, maintaining the integrity of the blinding throughout the data handling and analysis phases. An independent group of researchers, separate from the clinical team, will be responsible for assessing the study outcomes. They will receive anonymized data, ensuring they remain unaware of the participants' group assignments.

Statistical methods used to compare groups.

The data collected will be continuous and longitudinal, as it involves measuring cognitive performance over time. The confidence interval will be 95% with a p-value <0.05.

This RCT will adhere to an intention-to-treat analysis framework, ensuring that all participants are analyzed within the groups to which they were originally assigned, regardless of adherence.

Descriptive analysis

Firstly a descriptive analysis of all variables will be performed. Continuous variables will be expressed as means and standard deviation for each group. Categorical variables such as “sex”, “APOE4 status” or “educational level” will be expressed as frequencies. All variables will be presented in tables for easy reference and comparison.

Qualitative Variables

- Sex:** Categorical variable indicating male or female participants.
- Educational Level:** Dichotomous variable (superior education or no).
- APOE ε4 Status:** Dichotomous variable indicating the presence or absence of the APOE ε4 allele (carrier or non-carrier).

Quantitative Variables

Primary Outcomes

-PACC Scores: Continuous variable, with higher scores indicating better cognitive function.

-FCSRT Scores: Continuous variable for memory assessment, with the score range from 0 to 48, where higher scores represent better memory performance.

-MMSE Scores: Continuous variable with a maximum score of 30, used to provide a general measure of cognitive function.

Secondary Outcomes:

-MRI Brain Volumetrics: Continuous variable with units in cubic centimeters (cc/cm³).

-FDG-PET: Continuous variable that reflects the cerebral metabolic rate of glucose in standard uptake value ratios (SUVr), which are unitless.

-Plasma and CSF Biomarkers: Concentrations measured in picomoles per milliliter (pmol/mL).

For these primary and secondary outcomes, means will be calculated for each of the three groups (G1, G2, and the control group) and compared at different time points during the study.

Basal analysis

Following randomization and prior to the commencement of interventions, we will perform a baseline analysis to demonstrate the equivalence of the groups. This will involve a comparison of demographic data (sex, age, educational level) and initial cognitive scores across Group 1 (G1), Group 2 (G2), and the Control group. The objective is to compare demographic and initial cognitive scores across the groups to confirm they are similar at the start, as expected after randomization. Differences, if any, will be noted and adjusted for in the final analysis to ensure accurate results.

Primary analysis

Primary outcome

In this RCT, we will analyze the the change in cognitive performance over a 26-month period through the PACC and the FCSRT as the main measures for this

change. The MMSE will serve as a supplementary role due to its lower sensitivity to early cognitive changes.

Participants are grouped into three categories: Group 1 (G1), Group 2 (G2), and a Control group.

The analysis will consist of:

- Comparing the mean scores at different time points across the three groups for the PACC, the FCSRT and the MMSE.
- Employing repeated measures ANOVA to determine the significance of changes in cognitive performance over time.

Secondary outcomes

To analyze MRI brain volumetrics and structure, we will report mean values expressed in cubic millimeters (mm^3) or cubic centimeters (cc/cm^3), utilizing repeated measures ANOVA across designated time checkpoints (**annex 4**).

Alongside it, we will monitor plasma levels of biomarkers such as p-Tau 217, A β 40, A β 42, Neurofilament Light Chain (NFL), and Glial Fibrillary Acidic Protein (GFAP) throughout the study duration. Furthermore, Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF) levels of A β 40, A β 42, Total Tau (T-tau), and Phosphorylated Tau (P-Tau 217) will be evaluated in conjunction with FDG-PET scans. These comprehensive assessments will similarly employ repeated measures ANOVA, taking into account the mean values at specified time intervals.

Subanalysis

Dose-response relationship of the AMBAR therapy

In evaluating the dose-response relationship, a categorical analysis will be conducted to compare the outcomes between the different treatment groups, G1 and G2, and the Control group. This analysis will categorize changes in biomarker levels and cognitive scores based on the specific treatment doses administered (20gr vs 40gr). We will then assess for any trend in the response that correlates with the ascending order of dosage categories from the Control group to G1 and G2, examining if and how the intensity of the treatment influences the results over time.

Z-scores of the neuropsychological batteries

In addition to the primary analytical methods, Z-scores will be calculated for the PACC, FCSRT, and MMSE outcomes to standardize cognitive performance scores relative to baseline measures. This will facilitate the detection of subtle changes in cognitive performance within our sample over the 26-month period and enable comparisons with standardized data.

To calculate the Z-scores for the PACC, FCSRT, and MMSE outcomes, we will first determine the mean and standard deviation of the baseline scores for each test. Each participant's subsequent scores will then be standardized by subtracting the baseline mean from their raw score and dividing the result by the baseline standard deviation. This process will convert the raw scores into a Z-score that reflects the number of standard deviations a participant's score is from the mean, providing a clear indication of how much change has occurred in cognitive performance relative to the average baseline performance.

The formula to calculate the z-score is :

$$Z = (X - b)/d$$

Where :

- X is the raw score we want to standardise.
- b is the mean baseline score of the control group.
- d is the standard deviation of the baseline scores of the control group.

Methods for subgroup analyses

Subgroup analyses will be conducted to evaluate the effects of the intervention within the pre-specified categories of participants, based on APOE ε4 status (carrier or non-carrier) and superior education level (yes or no). The subgroup analyses will utilize the same repeated measures ANOVA approach as the primary analysis with time as the response variable.

Other assessments

Patient adherence rates will be assessed through patient self-reports at each visit to provide a measure of compliance with the treatment regimen.

The incidence of treatment-related adverse events will be tracked and documented using a standardized adverse event (AE) reporting form, which categorizes events by severity and likely association with the treatment (24).

Adverse events will be classified as follows to ensure consistent documentation and response:

Severity	Description	Required action
Mild	Local catheter reactions – Dizziness - Presyncope - Nausea - Muscle spasms - Paresthesia - Contusion - Anxiety - Blood fibrinogen decreased- Blood/venous pressure decreased.	Monitor and report if changes occur.
Moderate	Hypotension - Anemia - Catheter/device infection	Requires treatment or adjustment of study protocol.
Severe	Serious adverse events (SAE) associated with IVIG – ARIA - Deaths (sepsis and suicide)	Requires immediate treatment and may lead to discontinuation from the study.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

To address the challenge of blinding in this study, given the nature of AMBAR therapy involving peripheral devices, two key strategies were implemented. First, both the active treatment and the placebo were administered in such a way that participants could not distinguish between the two, thereby maintaining participant blinding and minimizing potential dropout bias. Second, to ensure the integrity of this approach, care providers received extensive training and were provided with detailed visual guides to perform both sham and actual procedures consistently, safeguarding the blinding of outcome assessments. These measures effectively mitigate the limitations posed by the intervention's design that could result in a higher drop-out rate in the placebo group.

On another hand, considering the slow and gradual clinical progression of preclinical AD, there is a possibility that the usual 14 months timeframe of the AMBAR protocol may not capture significant differences between the treatment and control groups. To

address this potential limitation, an additional 12 follow-up period was added to detect treatment effects. Furthermore, eligibility criteria were refined to include patients characterized as A+T+N+ or A+T+N-, the biomarker profiles indicative of a higher likelihood of rapid cognitive decline during the study's duration. Moreover, to reinforce our approach, participants also have to meet specific neuropsychological criteria, performing >1.5 standard deviations below the norm for their age, gender, and educational level on cognitive assessments.

Another limitation of this study is the potential "learning effect" on repeated neuropsychological assessments such as the PACC, FCSRT, and MMSE, which is of particular concern in a preclinical AD population known for higher cognitive performance. To address this, we introduced a six-month interval between test administrations of these tests, ensuring that improvements in test scores more accurately reflect genuine cognitive changes rather than mere familiarity with the tests.

The financial outlay required for this trial, potentially reaching hundred of thousands euros, constitutes a limitation. However, it is essential to acknowledge that, with the expected doubling of AD cases to nearly two million individuals by 2050 in Spain alone (2), the investment in such research could pale in comparison to the escalating costs of untreated Alzheimer's across healthcare, social care, and the wider economy. Thus, while the cost of this study is substantial, the potential for AMBAR therapy to mitigate the long-term economic impact of AD provides a strong justification for the upfront investment.

Ultimately, while this study's 26-month duration, including a 14-month treatment phase and a 12-month follow-up, offers valuable initial insights, it may not capture the full spectrum of the long-term effects of AMBAR. Recognizing this limitation, a future prospective cohort study using the same patient population could provide critical information on the long-term evolution and management needs. Such research would explore the necessity and timing of periodic AMBAR treatments.

ESTIMATED IMPACT

The goal of this trial extends beyond improving patient outcomes; it is to recalibrate the societal and clinical approaches to dementia. By demonstrating the efficacy of AMBAR therapy in high-risk groups, we advocate for a change in the management of Alzheimer's disease, emphasizing prevention and early intervention. Such a paradigm shift has the potential to destigmatize dementia and inspire a more dignified view of aging within our society.

The anticipated impact of AMBAR therapy offers substantial value to various parties in the context of preclinical AD. This therapy could potentially enable patients to retain their cognitive abilities longer, directly benefiting their daily living and social engagement. By maintaining cognitive function, patients may live with a sense of autonomy and contribution lessening the emotional and practical burdens often shouldered by families or caregivers.

From a healthcare perspective, the adoption of AMBAR therapy could lead to a more efficient allocation of medical resources. By slowing the progression of AD in high-risk populations, the therapy may reduce the need for extensive nursing care and frequent medical interventions, resulting in direct healthcare cost savings. Additionally, the mitigation of the burden of Alzheimer's would also translate into lower indirect costs known as "opportunity costs", related to the loss of productivity for both patients and caregivers, as well as lower direct social care costs, intangible costs and informal care costs.

Furthermore, the successful implementation of AMBAR therapy in clinical practice would deepen the importance of proactive healthcare strategies, promoting healthier aging across the population. It could help disassociate the process of aging from neurological decline, challenging prevailing narratives that deem cognitive deterioration as an inevitable aspect of growing older.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This randomized controlled trial is conducted in concordance with the current ethical standards and regulations. It is in full compliance with the International Ethical Guidelines for Biomedical Research Involving Human Subjects, the Declaration of Helsinki, and pertinent EU regulations regarding human health research. The personal data handling will conform to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) updates, ensuring the protection of all participants' digital and personal rights concerning data handling and privacy.

As this study involves the collection of biological samples such as blood and CSF, we adhere strictly to the updated directives on biological sample management, ensuring all samples are handled with care and disposed of properly post-analysis. Each hospital's ethical review board (**annex 3**) would have to approve all study protocols, and informed consent is obtained from all participants, either in writing or verbally, as per their preference and in the presence of an ethics committee representative.

The informed consent form is fundamental in our study given the invasive nature of the AMBAR therapy procedures like lumbar puncture, blood analysis and plasmapheresis, alongside imaging and cognitive testing. It ensures participants are fully aware of the research, their involvement, and the retention of their data and samples for extended analysis. The form upholds their autonomy and rights, detailing the protection of their information in line with GDPR, while allowing them to make an informed decision about their voluntary participation over the 26-month study period.

Participants will be informed in detail about the study's objectives, its voluntary nature, and the confidentiality of data through an information document. They will be advised that their data may be stored for a period extending up to 10 years post-study for follow-up and analysis as per current regulatory guidelines.

In summary, this trial is committed to maintaining the highest ethical standards, ensuring participant confidentiality and data integrity while contributing valuable research insights into the treatment and management of preclinical AD.

EXPECTED RESULTS

Primary outcomes

The anticipated results are based on hypothesized effect sizes that are derived from observed trends in Alzheimer's disease progression and responses to the AMBAR treatment (5,23,24). We have established the following expectations for our primary outcomes, considering a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ (p-value < 0.05) and a 95% confidence interval.

Control Group (Group C):Based on the natural progression observed in AD (5), it's reasonable to expect a negative effect size (d-cohen [-0.2,-0.8]), as seen in the placebo group of the AMBAR trial, reflecting the rapid progression of the condition without treatment.

Low Dose Treatment Group (Group G2): Drawing parallels from the AMBAR study's low-albumin group (23,24), a small to medium positive effect size (d-cohen [0.2 to 0.5]) could be anticipated for the low dose treatment group, indicating a deceleration of disease progression.

High Dose Treatment Group (Group G1): In line with the outcomes for the high-albumin group in the AMBAR trial (23,24), a medium to large positive effect size (d-cohen [0.5 to 0.8]) might be hypothesized for the high dose treatment group, suggesting a more pronounced slowing of the disease's progression.

The following tables and graphs are illustrative estimates of the results we expect to observe within our study population. The baseline scores represent typical starting points for our target sample (P3PAD), while the anticipated results show expected trends and potential outcomes.

PACC	G1	G2	C
Baseline Visit	90	90	90
Month 6	91	90	87
Month 12	92	91	83
Month 18	92	91	82
Month 26	92	91	81

FCSRT	G1	G2	C
Baseline Visit	42	42	42
Month 6	43	43	40
Month 12	44	43	37
Month 18	44	43	35
Month 26	44	43	32

MMSE	G1	G2	C
Baseline Visit	29	29	29
Month 6	29	29	29
Month 12	29	29	28
Month 18	29	29	27
Month 26	29	29	25

**These tables and graphs are purely speculative and solely serve as a visual illustration of our expected results.*

Secondary outcomes

Plasma Biomarkers

- **p-Tau 217:** We anticipate a significant reduction in plasma p-Tau 217 levels immediately following the intensive phase of the AMBAR therapy, with a smaller reduction during the maintenance phase, stabilizing during the follow-up period.
- **GFAP & NFL:** Similar to p-Tau 217, we expect a substantial decrease in GFAP and NFL levels, indicating a reduction in neuroinflammation and neurodegeneration, with a stabilization in the follow-up phase.
- **Plasma A β 40/A β 42 Ratio:** We anticipate that AMBAR therapy will improve the plasma A β 40/A β 42 ratio, reflecting reduced amyloid-beta deposition in the brain, due to the anticipated increased clearance and decreased aggregation of A β 42.

MRI Measurements:

- **Hippocampal Volume:** We predict a stabilization in hippocampal volume in treated groups compared to an anticipated decrease in the control group. This would suggest a protective effect of the therapy against the hippocampal atrophy typically observed in Alzheimer's progression.
- **White Matter Hyperintensities (WMH):** We anticipate that AMBAR therapy will slow the progression of WMH compared to the control, reflecting its potential to preserve vascular integrity and reduce neuroinflammation in the brain.

CSF Biomarkers

- **A β 40/A β 42 ratio :** We expect the AMBAR therapy to stabilize or possibly improve the A β 40/A β 42 ratio, suggesting a modulatory effect on amyloid-beta deposition dynamics.
- **T-tau and p-Tau :** We expect AMBAR therapy to decrease CSF levels of t-tau and p-tau, suggesting a potential reduction in neuronal damage and tau pathology.

FDG-PET scans

We predict a stabilization or increase of glucose metabolism in brain regions affected by Alzheimer's in treated groups compared to controls, indicating of sustained neuronal activity and metabolic function.

ABBREVIATIONS

AD: Alzheimer's Disease.

NIA-AA: US National Institute on Aging-Alzheimer's Association

MCI: Mild Cognitive Impairment

P3-PAD: Phase 3 Preclinical Alzheimer's Disease

ATN: Classification system evaluating AD's biomarkers in three distinct groups: Amyloid pathology, Tau pathology, and Neurodegeneration or neuronal injury.

ADAS-Cog: Alzheimer's Disease Assessment Scale-Cognitive Subscale

PACC: Preclinical Alzheimer's Cognitive Composite

FCSRT: Free and Cued Selective Reminding Test .

A β : Amyloid-beta

p-Tau 181: Phosphorylated Tau at position

T-Tau: Total Tau

NFL: Neurofilament Light Chain

GFAP: Glial Fibrillary Acidic Protein

ARIA-E: Amyloid-related imaging abnormalities with edema

ARIA-H: Amyloid-related imaging abnormalities with microbleeds

MRI: Magnetic Resonance Imaging

FDG-PET: Fluorodeoxyglucose Positron Emission Tomography

WMH: White Matter Hyperintensities

CSF: Cerebrospinal Fluid

IVIG: Intravenous Immunoglobulin

QoL-AD: Quality of Life in Alzheimer's Disease .

TPE: Therapeutic Plasma Exchange .

LVPE: Low Volume Plasma Exchange .

LOPDGDD: Organic Law on the Protection of Personal Data and Guarantee of Digital Rights .

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation .

AE: Adverse effects

CEIC: Investigation by the ethics committee

BV: Baseline visit

FV: Follow-up visit

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ANNEX 1 : BIBLIOGRAPHIC RECORDS

1) Bibliografia	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Zhang XX, Tian Y, Wang ZT, Ma YH, Tan L, Yu JT. The Epidemiology of Alzheimer's Disease Modifiable Risk Factors and Prevention. J Prev Alzheimers Dis. 2021;8(3):313-321.
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article presents an overview of the epidemiology of Alzheimer's Disease, focusing on modifiable risk factors and potential prevention strategies.
Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Observational
Disseny de l'estudi	Systematic review
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH Terms] OR "Alzheimer's"[All Fields]) AND ("Epidemiology"[MeSH Terms] OR "Epidemiology"[All Fields]) AND ("Risk Factors"[MeSH Terms] OR "Modifiable Risk Factors"[All Fields]) AND ("Prevention and Control"[MeSH Terms] OR "Prevention"[All Fields])
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This article is crucial for my study as it highlights the rising prevalence of Alzheimer's globally and emphasizes the importance of early preventive measures in non-demented individuals, aligning with the aim of the RCT to intervene at the preclinical stage.

2) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Lloret A, Esteve D, Lloret MA, et al. When Does Alzheimer's Disease Really Start? The Role of Biomarkers. Int J Mol Sci. 2019;20(22):5536.
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article discusses the early detection of Alzheimer's disease through biomarkers, indicating that AD pathology begins well before clinical symptoms are apparent.
Tipus de document	Journal Article
Tipus d'estudi	Observational
Disseny de l'estudi	Systematic review
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH Terms] OR "Alzheimer's"[All Fields]) AND ("Disease Progression"[MeSH Terms] OR "Preclinical"[All Fields]) AND ("Practice Guideline"[Publication Type] OR "Recommendations"[All Fields] OR "Consensus"[All Fields])

Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This review supports the premise that AD begins years before clinical symptoms, reinforcing the need for early detection and intervention, which is central to the rationale of my study.
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3) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	DeTure MA, Dickson DW. The neuropathological diagnosis of Alzheimer's Disease. Mol Neurodegener, 2019; 14:32
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article provides insights into the neuropathological criteria for Alzheimer's Disease diagnosis, emphasizing the pivotal role of amyloid-beta plaques and TAU protein neurofibrillary tangles in AD pathogenesis.
Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Observational
Disseny de l'estudi	Literature review
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	I identified the article as a relevant reference within the "Dubois et al. Biomarkers in Alzheimer's Disease: role in early and differential diagnosis and recognition of atypical variants."
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This article underpins the neuropathological understanding of Alzheimer's, substantiating the amyloid hypothesis and tau pathology, which is fundamental for my study's focus on early disease markers and progression.

4) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Jack CR Jr, Bennett DA, Blennow K, Carrillo MC, Dunn B, Haeberlein SB, et al. NIA-AA Research Framework: Toward a biological definition of Alzheimer's disease. Alzheimers Dement. 2018 Apr;14(4):535-562
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article discusses an update to the Alzheimer's disease (AD) diagnostic guidelines by the NIA-AA, emphasizing a biomarker-based definition of AD and outlining a research framework for studying AD as a continuum.
Tipus de document	Review article
Tipus d'estudi	Observational
Disseny de l'estudi	Systematic review / Conceptual framework
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH Terms]) AND ("NIA-AA Research Framework"[All Fields] OR "biological definition of Alzheimer's disease"[All Fields])

Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This framework underpins the biological construct of AD crucial for my study's emphasis on biomarker-based early detection and intervention in AD's continuum. As well as the importance of a shift from AD being a purely clinical entity to a biological one diagnosed with the use of biomarkers in CSF.
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5) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Jessen F, Amariglio RE, van Boxtel M, Breteler M, Ceccaldi M, Chételat G, et al. A conceptual framework for research on subjective cognitive decline in preclinical Alzheimer's disease. <i>Alzheimers Dement.</i> 2014 Nov;10(6):844-852
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article reviews the evolution of Alzheimer's disease diagnostic criteria, emphasizing the role of biomarkers in identifying the disease in its preclinical stage and conceptualizing AD as a dynamic disease continuum that spans from preclinical stages to dementia.
Tipus de documento	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Observational
Disseny de l'estudi	Systematic review / Conceptual framework
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH Terms] OR "Alzheimer's"[All Fields]) AND ("Subjective Cognitive Decline"[All Fields] OR "SCD"[All Fields]) AND ("Preclinical Alzheimer's disease"[All Fields] OR "Early Diagnosis"[MeSH Terms])
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This article provides critical insight into the early manifestation of AD, underscoring the limitations of traditional cognitive assessments and the need for more sensitive and nuanced detection methods.

6) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Hobart J, Cano S, Posner H, Selnes O, Stern Y, Thomas R, et al. Putting the Alzheimer's cognitive test to the test I: traditional psychometric methods. <i>Alzheimers Dement.</i> 2013 Feb;9(1 Suppl):S4-9
Idea general que transmet l'article	This study's critique of the ADAS-Cog highlights the need for sensitive cognitive measures in early AD.

Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Observational
Disseny de l'estudi	Cross sectional
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH Terms]) AND ("Psychometrics"[MeSH Terms] OR "Psychometric Tests"[All Fields] OR "Cognitive Tests"[MeSH Terms])
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	The study highlights the ADAS-Cog's insensitivity in early AD stages, underscoring the need for more sensitive tools. This justifies the use of other cognitive tests in this RCT.

7) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Papp KV, Rofael H, Veroff AE, Donohue MC, Wang S, Randolph C, et al. Sensitivity of the Preclinical Alzheimer's Cognitive Composite (PACC), PACC5, and Repeatable Battery for Neuropsychological Status (RBANS) to Amyloid Status in Preclinical Alzheimer's Disease - Atabecestat Phase 2b/3 EARLY Clinical Trial. J Prev Alzheimers Dis. 2022;9(2):255-61.
Idea general que transmet l'article	This article explores the effectiveness of various cognitive assessment tools in detecting early signs of Alzheimer's disease, focusing on their sensitivity and specificity in relation to amyloid status.
Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Observational
Disseny de l'estudi	Cross-sectional study
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Preclinical Alzheimer's disease"[Title/Abstract] OR "PACC"[Title/Abstract] OR "RBANS"[Title/Abstract]) AND ("cognitive assessment"[Title/Abstract] OR "amyloid"[Title/Abstract])
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This study validates the utility of cognitive composites like PACC and FCSRT in identifying preclinical AD with high sensitivity and specificity, essential for my research on early detection.

8) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Sperling RA, Jack CR Jr, Aisen PS. Testing the right target and right drug at the right stage. Sci Transl Med. 2011 Nov 30;3(111):111cm33
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article discusses strategies for testing Alzheimer's disease treatments at appropriate disease stages and targets, emphasizing the importance of timing and specificity in therapeutic interventions.
Tipus de documento	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Analytical
Disseny de l'estudi	Author manuscript
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	I identified the article as a relevant reference within the study 'Identification of preclinical dementia according to ATN classification for stratified trial recruitment: A machine learning approach' by Koychev I et al.
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	The article informs my study's approach by detailing the necessity of stage-specific intervention, aligning with my research on early-stage Alzheimer's intervention efficacy.

9) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Oddo S, Billings L, Kesslak JP, Cribbs DH, LaFerla FM. Abeta immunotherapy leads to clearance of early, but not late, hyperphosphorylated tau aggregates via the proteasome. Neuron. 2004 Aug 5;43(3):321-32.
Idea general que transmet l'article	The study demonstrates that A β immunotherapy can clear early tau pathology in a triple transgenic mouse model of Alzheimer's, suggesting a window for effective intervention before MCI phase.
Tipus de documento	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Experimental
Disseny de l'estudi	Preclinical study on animals
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH Terms]) AND ("Immunotherapy"[MeSH Terms] OR "Antibodies"[MeSH Terms]) AND ("tau Proteins"[MeSH Terms] OR "Neurofibrillary Tangles"[MeSH Terms]) AND ("Mice, Transgenic"[MeSH Terms])
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This study's findings on early intervention efficacy are integral to my research on the timing of therapeutic strategies in pre-MCI Alzheimer's disease.

10) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Cuberas-Borrós G, Roca I, Castell-Conesa J, Núñez L, Boada M, López OL, et al. Neuroimaging analyses from a randomized controlled study to evaluate plasma exchange with albumin replacement in mild-to-moderate Alzheimer's disease: additional results from the AMBAR study. Eur J Nucl Med Mol Imaging. 2022;49:4589–4600
Idea general que transmet l'article	These additional results from the AMBAR study aimed to analyse structural and functional brain changes through MRI volumetric analyses and 18F-fluorodeoxyglucose positron emission tomography (18FDG-PET)
Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Experimental
Disseny de l'estudi	RCT
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH Terms] OR "Alzheimer's"[All Fields]) AND ("Albumins"[MeSH Terms] OR "Albumin"[All Fields]) AND ("Clinical Trial")
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This article justifies this RCT's strategy to recur to 18FDG-PET and MRI to evaluate patients' progression and/or the disease's stabilization.

11) Bibliografia	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Hansson O, Seibyl J, Stomrud E, Zetterberg H, Trojanowski JQ, Bittner T, et al. CSF biomarkers of Alzheimer's disease concord with amyloid-β PET and predict clinical progression: a study of fully automated immunoassays in BioFINDER and ADNI cohorts. Alzheimers Dement. 2018;14:1470–81.
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article presents a study showing that CSF biomarkers align with amyloid- β PET imaging results and can predict the clinical progression of Alzheimer's disease, highlighting the effectiveness of fully automated immunoassays in large cohort studies.
Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Observational
Disseny de l'estudi	Cohort study
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Cerebrospinal Fluid"[MeSH Terms] OR "csf"[All Fields]) AND ("Biomarkers"[MeSH Terms] OR "biomarkers"[All Fields]) AND ("Alzheimer

	Disease/diagnosis"[MeSH Terms] OR "Alzheimer Disease/pathology"[MeSH Terms] OR "Alzheimer's disease"[All Fields]) AND ("Amyloid beta-Peptides"[MeSH Terms] OR "amyloid"[All Fields])
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This study is integral to my research as it underscores the diagnostic utility of CSF biomarkers, such as A β 42, A β 40, pTau181, pTau217, and tTau, in detecting AD pathology early.

12) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Ferreira PCL, Therriault J, Tissot C, Ferrari-Souza JP, Benedet AL, Povala G, et al. Plasma p-tau231 and p-tau217 inform on tau tangles aggregation in cognitively impaired individuals. <i>Alzheimers Dement.</i> 2023;19(10):4463-4474.
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article investigates the efficacy of plasma phosphorylated tau (p-tau) biomarkers (specifically p-tau231 and p-tau217+) in detecting amyloid- β (A β) and tau pathologies across different cognitive states. It demonstrates that in cognitively unimpaired individuals, these biomarkers, alongside demographic information (age and sex), significantly improve the identification of A β pathology. However, in cognitively impaired individuals, p-tau231, p-tau217+, and Glial Fibrillary Acidic Protein (GFAP) offer valuable insights into both A β deposition and tau tangle accumulation, suggesting their role as indicators of disease progression from preclinical to symptomatic Alzheimer's Disease stages
Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Observational
Disseny de l'estudi	Cross-sectional study
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	"tau Proteins"[MeSH] AND "Amyloid beta-Peptides"[MeSH] AND "Biomarkers"[MeSH] AND ("Cognitive Dysfunction"[MeSH] OR "Cognition Disorders"[MeSH]) AND "Positron-Emission Tomography"[MeSH]
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This article validates the use of plasma p-tau217 as a sensitive biomarker for early detection and monitoring of preclinical Alzheimer's Disease, highlighting its efficacy in identifying amyloid-beta deposition and tau pathology progression from asymptomatic stages to clinical Alzheimer's.

13) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Kim KY, Shin KY, Chang K-A. GFAP as a Potential Biomarker for Alzheimer's Disease: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. Cells. 2023;12:1309.
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article discusses GFAP (Glial Fibrillary Acidic Protein) not only as a potential biomarker for Alzheimer's Disease (AD) but also highlights its significance in the context of inflammation within the brain. This systematic review and meta-analysis, explores the correlation between GFAP levels in peripheral blood and the presence of AD.
Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Observational
Disseny de l'estudi	Systematic review and meta-analysis
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	"Glial Fibrillary Acidic Protein"[MeSH] AND "Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH] AND "Biomarkers"[MeSH] AND "Inflammation"[MeSH]
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	GFAP elevation in plasma reflects astrocyte activation and blood-brain barrier disruption, indicating its potential as a biomarker for neuroinflammation and Alzheimer's Disease progression, making it valuable for clinical trials targeting inflammatory pathways and AD diagnosis.

14) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Lehmann S, Schraen-Maschke S, Vidal JS, Blanc F, Paquet C, Allinquant B, et al.; BALTAZAR Study Group. Blood Neurofilament Levels Predict Cognitive Decline across the Alzheimer's Disease Continuum. Int J Mol Sci. 2023 Dec 11;24(24):17361
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article investigates Neurofilament light chain (NfL) as a plasma biomarker for diagnosing and prognosticating Alzheimer's disease (AD) and Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI). It finds that baseline plasma NfL levels rise across the AD continuum, correlating with cognitive decline and demographic factors, indicating its potential for monitoring cognitive status and progression in AD.
Tipus de document	Journal article

Tipus d'estudi	Observational
Disseny de l'estudi	Prospective cohort study
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	"Neurofilament Proteins"[MeSH] AND "Cognitive Dysfunction"[MeSH] AND "Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH] AND "Biomarkers"[MeSH]
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This article underscores the significance of Neurofilament light chain (NfL) in plasma as a reliable biomarker for tracking cognitive decline in Alzheimer's Disease (AD), particularly valuable for monitoring patients in preclinical stages.

15) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Chowdhury S, Chowdhury NS. Novel anti-amyloid-beta (Aβ) monoclonal antibody lecanemab for Alzheimer's disease: A systematic review. Int J Immunopathol Pharmacol. 2023 Jan-Dec;37:3946320231209839
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article systematically reviews the efficacy and safety of lecanemab, a novel anti-amyloid-beta monoclonal antibody, in the treatment of Alzheimer's disease, including potential risks and benefits.
Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Observational
Disseny de l'estudi	Systematic review
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH Terms]) AND (("Immunotherapy"[MeSH Terms]) OR "Antibodies, Monoclonal"[MeSH Terms]) AND ("Clinical Trials, Phase III as Topic"[MeSH Terms] OR "FDA"[All Fields])
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This review is vital as it encompasses the therapeutic potential and challenges of lecanemab, particularly ARIA risks, which informs the safety considerations in the study.

16) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Prajapati KD, Sharma SS, Roy N. Current perspectives on potential role of albumin in neuroprotection. Rev Neurosci. 2011;22(3):355-63. doi: 10.1515/RNS.2011.028. Epub 2011 May 13.
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article reviews the neuroprotective roles of albumin, emphasizing its multifunctional properties, including antioxidant effects, which

	may have therapeutic implications in neurological diseases.
Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Observational
Disseny de l'estudi	Literature review
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Albumin"[MeSH Terms] OR "Albumin"[All Fields]) AND ("Neuroprotective Agents"[MeSH Terms] OR "Neuroprotection"[All Fields])
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This review substantiates the neuroprotective attributes of albumin, particularly its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory capacities, which are integral to the study's focus on therapeutic strategies in neurodegenerative conditions.

17) Bibliografia	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	DeMattos RB, Bales KR, Cummins DJ, Dodart JC, Paul SM, Holtzman DM. Peripheral anti-A beta antibody alters CNS and plasma A beta clearance and decreases brain A beta burden in a mouse model of Alzheimer's disease. Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A. 2001 Jul 17;98(15):8850-5
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article explores how peripheral anti-A β antibody administration alters CNS and plasma A β clearance and reduces brain A β burden in a mouse model, supporting the 'peripheral sink hypothesis' in Alzheimer's disease.
Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Experimental
Disseny de l'estudi	Preclinical study on animals
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH Terms]) AND ("Antibodies"[MeSH Terms]) AND ("Mice"[MeSH Terms])
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This study is essential for my research as it underlines the potential of leveraging the peripheral sink mechanism of A β clearance as a therapeutic strategy for Alzheimer's disease.

18) Bibliografia	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	DeMattos RB, Bales KR, Cummins DJ, Paul SM, Holtzman DM. Brain to plasma amyloid-beta efflux: a measure of brain amyloid burden in a mouse model of Alzheimer's disease. Science. 2002 Mar 22;295(5563):2264-7
Idea general que transmet l'article	This study examines the process of amyloid-beta clearance from the brain to the plasma,

	contributing further evidence to the 'peripheral sink hypothesis' in Alzheimer's disease.
Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Experimental
Disseny de l'estudi	Preclinical study on animals
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH Terms]) AND ("Amyloid beta-Peptides"[MeSH Terms]) AND ("Biological Transport"[MeSH Terms])
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This article underscores the foundational research supporting the peripheral sink hypothesis, which is central to my study's intervention strategy.

19) Bibliografia	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Matsuoka Y, Saito M, LaFrancois J, Saito M, Gaynor K, Olm V, et al. Novel therapeutic approach for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease by peripheral administration of agents with an affinity to beta-amyloid. J Neurosci. 2003 Jan 1;23(1):29-33
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article explores a novel treatment strategy for Alzheimer's disease, focusing on the reduction of brain amyloid levels through the peripheral administration of agents that bind to beta-amyloid, suggesting an alternative to traditional immunotherapy approaches.
Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Experimental
Disseny de l'estudi	Preclinical study on animals
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH Terms] OR "Alzheimer's"[All Fields]) AND ("beta-Amyloid"[MeSH Terms] OR "A β "[All Fields]) AND ("Therapeutics"[MeSH Terms] OR "Therapy"[All Fields] OR "Treatment"[All Fields]) AND ("Peripheral Administration"[All Fields] OR "Peripheral Treatment"[All Fields])
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This study provides evidence supporting a therapeutic approach that diverges from direct SNC targeting interventions, potentially offering a safer and more accessible treatment pathway for Alzheimer's disease by targeting peripheral beta-amyloid.

20) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Biere AL, Ostaszewski B, Stimson ER, Hyman BT, Maggio JE et al.. Amyloid beta-peptide is transported on lipoproteins and albumin in human plasma. J Biol Chem. 1996 Dec 20;271(51):32916-22
Idea general que transmet l'article	The study investigates the transport of amyloid beta-peptide in human plasma, primarily associated with albumin and lipoproteins, under physiological conditions.
Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Analytical
Disseny de l'estudi	Biochemical assay
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	"Amyloid beta-Peptides"[MeSH Terms] AND "Albumins"[MeSH Terms]
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This study's findings on the binding affinity of albumin for A β peptides support the rationale for using albumin in therapeutic interventions for AD.

21) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Boada M, López O, Núñez L, Szczepiorkowski ZM, Torres M, Grifols C, et al. Plasma exchange for Alzheimer's disease Management by Albumin Replacement (AMBAR) trial: Study design and progress. Alzheimers Dement (N Y). 2019 Feb 26;5:61-69.
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article presents the AMBAR trial's design and its ongoing process, evaluating the effectiveness of plasma exchange in Alzheimer's treatment through albumin replacement.
Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Experimental
Disseny de l'estudi	Randomised Controlled Trial
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH Terms] OR "Alzheimer's"[All Fields]) AND ("Albumins"[MeSH Terms] OR "Albumin"[All Fields]) AND ("Clinical Trial")
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This study underpins the safety profile and manageable risks of AMBAR therapy with vigilant and adequate monitoring.

22) Bibliografia.	
Referència de l'article (format Vancouver)	Boada M, López OL, Olazarán J, Núñez L, Pfeffer M, Paricio M, et al. A randomized,

	controlled clinical trial of plasma exchange with albumin replacement for Alzheimer's disease: Primary results of the AMBAR Study. Alzheimers Dement. 2020 Oct;16(10):1412-1425
Idea general que transmet l'article	The article discusses the primary outcomes of the AMBAR study, which is a randomized controlled trial evaluating the efficacy of plasma exchange with albumin replacement in patients with mild to moderate Alzheimer's disease.
Tipus de document	Journal article
Tipus d'estudi	Experimental
Disseny de l'estudi	Randomised controlled trial
Estratègia de cerca utilitzada	("Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH Terms] OR "Alzheimer's"[All Fields]) AND ("Albumins"[MeSH Terms] OR "Albumin"[All Fields]) AND ("Clinical Trial")
Per que és important pel teu estudi (màxim 50 paraules)	This study is pivotal as it showcases the progression of the AMBAR treatment through advanced clinical trial phases, indicating a significant impact on Alzheimer's disease management in mild to moderate AD, but also notes that the comprehensive benefits of albumin replacement therapy are yet to be fully delineated.

ANNEX 2: TABLES OF VARIABLES

	Variable name	Description	Type	Time points	Units	Additional details
Participant demographics	Participant ID	Unique for each participant	Categorical	Enrollment	N/A	Used to de-identify data
	Age	Participants age	Continuous	At signing of the informed consent	Years	N/A
	Sex	Participant's sex	Categorical	Baseline	N/A	Male/Female
	APOE ε4 status	Presence of APOE ε4 allele	Categorical	Baseline	Positive/Negative	Genetic test result
	Education level	Superior education attained	Categorical	Baseline	N/A	Yes/no

	Variable name	Description	Type	Time points	Units	Additional details
Primary Outcome measures	PACC score	Preclinical Alzheimer Cognitive Composite Score	Continuous	Baseline, every 6 months	Standardised core (100)	Multiple cognitive domains' assessment
	FCSRT Score	Free and Cued Selective Reminding Test Score	Continuous	Baseline, week 6, every 6 monthd	Score (0-48)	Memory assessment
	MMSE score	Mini-mental State Examination score	Continuous	Baseline, every 6 months	Score (0-30)	Supplementary role due to lower sensitivity MCI threshold < 26.

	Variable name	Description	Type	Time points	Units	Additional details
Secondary Outcomes measures	MRI measurements	7 variables : hippocampal volume, posterior cingulate volume, entorhinal cortex volume, ventricular volume, total brain volume, and white matter hyperintensities (WMH) and small vessel health	Continuous	Baseline, end of each phase (week 6, month 14, month 26)	Cubic millimeters (mm ³)	Structural changes indicative of AD's progression
	FDG-PET	Brain activity mapping and metabolism	Continuous	Baseline, end of each phase (week 6, month 14, month 26)	Standardized Uptake Value (SUV)	Metabolic changes indicative of AD's progression
	CSF Aβ levels	A β 1-40 and A β 1-42 levels in cerebrospinal fluid. A β 42/A β 40 ratio.	Continuous	Baseline, end of each phase (week 6, month 14, month 26)	Concentration	Biomarker assessment Patient progression
	CSF Tau levels	p-Tau 217 and p-tau 181 and T-tau levels in CSF	Continuous	Baseline, end of each phase (week 6, month 14, month 26)	Concentration	Biomarker assessment Patient progression
	Plasma Aβ levels	A β 42/A β 40 ratio in plasma	Continuous	Before and after every PE and tri-annually during the follow-up phase	Concentration	Biomarker assessment Patient progression
	Plasma GFAP levels	GFAP concentration in plasma	Continuous	Before and after every PE and tri-annually during the follow-up phase	Concentration	Biomarker of neuroinflammation
	Plasma NFL concentration	NFL concentration in plasma	Continuous	Before and after every PE and tri-annually during the follow-up phase	Concentration	Biomarker of neuronal death /neurodegeneration
	Plasma p-Tau 217	p-Tau 217 concentration in plasma	Continuous	Before and after every PE and tri-annually during the follow-up phase	Concentration	Biomarker assessment Patient progression

	Variable name	Description	Type	Time points	Units	Additional details
Tolerability, adherence and quality of life	Adverse events	Record of any adverse events	Categorical	Throughout the study	N/A	Type and severity of event
	Treatment adherence	Compliance with treatment regimen	Categorical	Throughout the study	Percentage	Treatment logs
	Quality of life	Quality of life of the patient throughout the study	Continuous	Baseline, every 6 months	N/A	QoL-AD Questionnaire

ANNEX 3: LIST OF CENTERS

Name of the Hospital	Center's Category
ACE – Alzheimer Center Barcelona	Specialized center – Coordinating center
Hospital Clinic Barcelona	Third level center
Hospital Universitari de Bellvitge	Third level center
Hospital Universitari Vall d'Hebron	Third level center
Hospital de la Santa Creu I Sant Pau	Third level center
Hospital Universitario Marqués de Valdecilla	Third level center
Hospital Universitario La Paz	Third level center
Hospital General Universitario Gregorio Marañón	Third level center
Hospital Universitario Ramon y Cajal	Third level center
Hospital Universitario 12 de Octubre	Third level center
Hospital Universitario Infanta Sofia	Third level center
Hospital Universitario Navarra	Third level center
Hospital Universitario de Cruces - Osakidetza	Third level center
Hospital General de Segovia	Third level center
Hospital Universitario Virgen del Rocío (Sevilla)	Third level center
Hospital Universitario Joan XXIII	Third level center
Hospital Universitario Reina Sofia	Third level center
Hospital Universitario Galdakao-Usansolo	Third level center

ANNEX 4: TIMELINE OF TREATMENT AND INTERIM ANALYSES

ANNEX 5: DETAILED COMPONENTS OF THE PRECLINICAL ALZHEIMER'S COGNITIVE COMPOSITE (PACC)

Component	Domain	Weight	Description
Symbol Digit modalities	Perceptual Speed/Working Memory	0.26	Assesses attention, visual scanning, and motor speed. The test requires participants to match symbols with corresponding numbers, based on a key provided at the top of the test form. This task engages visual tracking and speed of information processing as the participant writes down or says aloud the corresponding number for each symbol. (25)
MMSE orientation to Time	Orientation	2.24	Assesses the patient's ability to correctly identify the current date, day of the week, month, season, and year. This section of the MMSE evaluates the patient's orientation to time, which can be affected in the early stages of cognitive decline, particularly in Alzheimer's disease.(24)
MMSE orientation to Place	Orientation	2.14	Assesses the patient's ability to correctly identify where they are, including the nature of the place (e.g., type of building, facility), the name of the place, the city, and sometimes even the floor or room, depending on the depth of the orientation assessment.(24)
Logical Memory Delayed Recall	Episodic memory	0.53	Part of the Logical Memory subtest from the Wechsler Memory Scale. Participants are read a story and asked to recall as much information as possible immediately after hearing it (Immediate Recall). After a delay, usually about 20-30 minutes during which time other tests are administered, participants are again asked to recall the story without having it reread to them (Delayed Recall). (25)
Word List-Delayed Recall	Episodic memory	1.36	A list of words is presented to the participant. The participant is asked to recall as many words as possible immediately after presentation (Immediate Recall). After a delay, during which other tasks may be performed, the participant is again asked to recall the words from the list (Delayed Recall). (25)
Judgment of Line Orientation	Visual spatial	0.68	Participants are shown an array of lines at different angles and are asked to match the orientation of these lines with a set of sample lines. The test usually consists of a series of items, each with two lines on a page that the participant must match from a choice of lines depicted in an arc. Scoring is based on the number of correct matches the participant makes. (25)

Raven's Progressive Matrices (9 items from A and B)	Visual spatial/working memory	1.39	<p>The subset of 9 items from sets A and B is a smaller version of the standard test, focusing on pattern recognition and logical reasoning using visual cues.</p> <p>Administration and Scoring:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Participants are shown a matrix or sequence with one element missing and are asked to select the missing piece from a set of options. -The test progresses in difficulty with each subsequent matrix. -The score is typically based on the number of correct selections out of the 9 items. (25)
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ANNEX 6: MINI-MENTAL STATE EXAMINATION (MMSE)

Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE)

Name	John Williams	Date	Feb 21, 2023
Instructions: Ask the questions in specified sequence and give one point for each correct response for each question or task.			
Questions	Maximum Score	Patient's Score	
1. "What year is this?" "What is the current season?" "What month is this?" "What's the date today?" "What day of the week it is?" (Score 1 point for each correct answer.)	5	3	
2. "Which country are we in right now?" "What state/province are we in?" "What city or town are we in?" "What city or town are we in?" "What's the street address of your home / What's the name of this building?" "On which floor are we located / In which room are currently located?" (Score 1 point for each correct answer.)	5	4	
3. "I'm going to name three words/objects and you need to repeat them. Then remember them because I'm going to ask you to name them again later." (EX: BALL - CAR - MAN / APPLE - PENNY - TABLE)	3	2	
4. "Spell WORLD backwards" Answer: D-L-R-O-W	5	4	
5. "Now, name the three objects/words I asked you to remember." (Give one point for each.)	3	3	
6. "What object is this?" Show a wrist watch.	1	1	
7. "What object is this?" Show a pencil.	1	0	
8. "Repeat this phrase: No ifs, ands, or buts. "	1	1	
9. "Read the words and then do what it says." (Give the patient/client a sheet of paper with CLOSE YOUR EYES written on it.)	1	1	
10. "Take the paper in your right/left hand, fold it in half, and put it on the floor." (Give the patient/client a piece of paper and score 1 for each action taken.)	3	3	
11. "Make up and write a complete sentence on a piece paper." (Sentence must contain a verb and noun.)	1	1	
12. "Copy this design, please." <div style="text-align: center;"> </div>	1	1	
TOTAL:	30	24	

INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

SCORE	DESCRIPTION	STAGE
30 - 26	normal	could be normal
25 - 20	mild	early
19 - 10	moderate	middle
9 - 0	severe	late

Folstein, M. F., Folstein, S. E., & McHugh, P. R. (1975). "Mini-mental state": A practical method for grading the cognitive state of patients for the clinician. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, 12(3), 189-198.

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ANNEX 7: QUALITY OF LIFE IN ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE (QOL-AD)

<p><i>UWMC/ADPRI/QOL</i> <i>Aging and Dementia: Quality of Life in AD</i> Quality of Life:AD (Participant Version)</p>					Score (for clinician's use only)
ID Number <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	Assessment Number <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	Interview Date <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> Month Day Year			
Instructions: Interviewer administer according to standard instructions. Circle your responses.					
1. Physical health	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	
2. Energy	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	
3. Mood	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	
4. Living situation	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	
5. Memory	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	
6. Family	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	
7. Marriage	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	
8. Friends	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	
9. Self as a whole	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	
10. Ability to do chores around the house	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	
11. Ability to do things for fun	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	
12. Money	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	
13. Life as a whole	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	
Comments: <hr/> <hr/>					Total

Logsdon RG. Quality of Life in Alzheimer's Disease (QOL-AD) questionnaire. Seattle, WA: University of Washington; 1996

ANNEX 8: HOJA INFORMATIVA DEL PACIENTE

Título del estudio: Ensayo Controlado Aleatorizado para Evaluar la Eficacia de la Terapia AMBAR en Retrasar el Declive Cognitivo en la Fase 3 Preclínica de la Enfermedad de Alzheimer: Enfoque en el Rendimiento Neuropsicológico y la Dinámica de Biomarcadores.

Estimado Participante,

Le invitamos a formar parte de un estudio de investigación clínica llevado a cabo por el Centro de Investigación y Alzheimer Center Fundació ACE - Institut Català de Neurociències Aplicades en Barcelona, en colaboración con la Universidad Internacional de Cataluña. Este estudio tiene como objetivo evaluar la efectividad de la terapia AMBAR para disminuir el declive cognitivo asociado con la enfermedad de Alzheimer preclínica fase 3. Si está experimentando cambios sutiles en su cognición (memoria, lenguaje, funciones ejecutivas u otros), podría calificar para participar en este estudio.

Visión General del Estudio

La investigación busca determinar si la terapia AMBAR puede posponer la progresión del declive cognitivo en la enfermedad de Alzheimer cuando la intervención se realiza temprano en su evolución. El ensayo utilizará evaluaciones neuropsicológicas y análisis de biomarcadores a lo largo de un periodo de 26 meses para medir el impacto del tratamiento.

Su Participación

Su implicación en el estudio es completamente voluntaria. Si decide tomar parte, será uno de los aproximadamente 237 participantes que ayudarán a proporcionar información valiosa sobre los beneficios potenciales de la terapia AMBAR. Será asignado aleatoriamente para recibir el tratamiento AMBAR o un placebo y se le solicitará completar varias pruebas y procedimientos diseñados para evaluar la eficacia del tratamiento.

Beneficios y Riesgos

Si bien el estudio puede o no ofrecer beneficios directos para su salud, su participación es invaluable para avanzar en nuestro conocimiento sobre la enfermedad de Alzheimer y potencialmente mejorar estrategias futuras de tratamiento.

En cuanto a los riesgos, estos varían desde reacciones leves como reacciones locales en el sitio del catéter, mareos, presíncope, náuseas, espasmos musculares, parestesia, contusión, ansiedad, disminución del fibrinógeno sanguíneo y disminución de la presión sanguínea/venosa, hasta riesgos moderados como hipotensión, anemia e infección del catéter/dispositivo. Aunque poco comunes, se han identificado eventos adversos graves asociados con el tratamiento, que incluyen complicaciones relacionadas con el uso de inmunoglobulina intravenosa (IVIG), anomalías relacionadas con amiloide observadas en imágenes (ARIA) y, en casos raros, defunciones debido a sepsis y suicidio.

La probabilidad de que ocurran estos efectos es baja, y nuestro equipo está preparado para manejarlos adecuadamente y garantizar su seguridad. Cualquier dato personal recopilado será manejado con estricto cumplimiento de las leyes y regulaciones de privacidad.

Lo que Deberá Hacer

Si opta por participar, se le pedirá que asista a visitas programadas del estudio y se someta a ciertos procedimientos, como evaluaciones cognitivas, análisis de sangre, punciones lumbares y estudios de imágenes. Recibirá información detallada sobre estos procedimientos por parte del equipo del estudio.

Costes

No hay obligación financiera para los participantes. El estudio financia todos los procedimientos de tratamiento.

Uso y Protección de Datos

Los datos recogidos serán estrictamente para investigación y se mantendrán confidencialmente bajo:

- La Ley Orgánica 3/2018, de 5 de diciembre, de Protección de Datos Personales y Garantía de los Derechos Digitales (LOPDGDD).
- El Reglamento General de Protección de Datos (UE) 2016/679.
- La Ley 41/2002, que regula la autonomía del paciente y los derechos y obligaciones en la información clínica.
- La Ley 14/2007 de investigación biomédica.
- El Real Decreto 1716/2011, que regula los biobancos y el uso de muestras biológicas en la investigación.

Estas regulaciones aseguran una protección rigurosa y derechos sobre los datos personales, incluyendo el derecho de acceso, rectificación, cancelación y oposición.

Financiación

Investigación apoyada por la Universidad Internacional de Cataluña.

Derechos del Participante

Usted mantiene todos los derechos sobre sus datos bajo LOPDGDD y GDPR, incluyendo acceso, rectificación, cancelación y oposición.

Confidencialidad

Todos los datos personales se almacenarán de manera segura y solo serán accesibles por personal autorizado, asegurando la privacidad y el cumplimiento con las leyes mencionadas.

Información Adicional

Este documento complementa pero no reemplaza las explicaciones verbales. Los participantes deben dirigir todas las consultas directamente al investigador principal.

Información de Contacto

Si tiene alguna pregunta o requiere más información sobre el estudio, por favor contacte al Centro de Investigación y Alzheimer Center Fundació ACE - Institut Català de Neurociències Aplicades en Barcelona.

Si está de acuerdo en participar, por favor brinde su consentimiento firmando el formulario de consentimiento adjunto.

Gracias por considerar su participación en este importante estudio. Su contribución podría conducir a avances significativos en el tratamiento de la enfermedad de Alzheimer.

Atentamente,

Nombre del Investigador Principal _____

Contacto del investigador principal _____

ANNEX 9: CONSENTIMIENTO INFORMADO

Formulario de Consentimiento del Paciente para la Participación en Investigación Clínica

Título del estudio: Ensayo Controlado Aleatorizado para Evaluar la Eficacia de la Terapia AMBAR en Retrasar el Declive Cognitivo en la Fase 3 Preclínica de la Enfermedad de Alzheimer: Enfoque en el Rendimiento Neuropsicológico y la Dinámica de Biomarcadores.

Yo, (Nombre del Paciente), por la presente reconozco y declaro que:

- He recibido información completa sobre el objetivo, los procedimientos, los posibles beneficios y los riesgos que conlleva la participación en el estudio mencionado.
- He tenido la oportunidad de realizar preguntas sobre el estudio, y todas mis inquietudes han sido resueltas a mi satisfacción por parte del investigador.
- Comprendo que mi participación en este estudio es voluntaria, y puedo retirarme en cualquier momento sin necesidad de justificar mi decisión y sin que ello afecte a mi atención médica o a mis derechos legales.
- Estoy informado sobre el tratamiento de mis datos personales conforme a la Ley Orgánica 3/2018 de Protección de Datos Personales y Garantía de los Derechos Digitales (LOPDGDD), el Reglamento General de Protección de Datos (GDPR) (UE) 2016/679, la Ley 41/2002 sobre la autonomía del paciente y los derechos y obligaciones en cuanto a la información y documentación clínica, y la Ley 14/2007 de investigación biomédica.
- Doy mi consentimiento para que mis datos personales y muestras biológicas sean recogidos, analizados y almacenados como se requiere para el estudio, de acuerdo con las directrices legales y éticas aplicables, incluyendo el RD 1716/2011 sobre Biobancos y la utilización de muestras en la investigación.
- Entiendo que los datos recogidos durante este estudio podrán ser compartidos con autoridades regulatorias, patrocinadores del estudio o colaboradores, de manera que se preserve mi anonimato, conforme a los requisitos legales.

- Acepto seguir los procedimientos y el calendario del estudio tal y como ha descrito el equipo de investigación.

Al firmar este formulario, doy mi consentimiento para participar en el estudio como se ha descrito y estoy de acuerdo con el uso de mis datos como se ha explicado anteriormente.

Firma del Participante: _____ Fecha: _____

Firma del Investigador Principal: _____ Fecha: _____

ANNEX 10: PARTICIPANTS FLOW

ANNEX 11: FLOW DIAGRAM

ANNEX 12: GANTT CHART OF THE STUDY

	2023				2024												2025												2026												2027											
Time in months	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Protocol Elaboration	█				█																																															
CEIC Approval									█																																											
Briefing neurologists and CAPs on the study													█																																							
Recruitment of participants													█				█																																			
Intervention																	█				█																															
Follow-up																					█				█																											
Data recollection																	█				█				█																											
Statistical analysis Discussion and publiaction of results																									█																											